

Supplementary Data, Tables, and Figures

Table S1. MIP clades as defined here based on phylogenetic trees from the ten data subsets and their reconstructed evolutionary origin (most recent common ancestor).

Table S2. Taxonomic distribution of selected MIP clades across eukaryotes with sequenced genomes in our dataset (it corresponds to Figure S15).

Table S3. Distribution of MIP homologs in our dataset for unicellular eukaryotes across here-defined paralogy clades, with emphasis on ‘MIP deep clades’ (MDC).

Table S4. Conserved amino acid residues for 127 defined MIP paralogy clades. Residues conserved in $\geq 90\%$ of the sequences are shown, indicating the corresponding coordinate and amino acid from the *E. coli* AqpZ sequence, as well as the amino acid conserved in the paralogy clade.

Table S4. Representative sequences for 127 defined MIP paralog clades, defined as those that retain all amino acids that are conserved in $\geq 90\%$ of the sequences.

Table S5. Taxonomic distribution of 32 Archaea MIP homologs from our dataset.

Table S6. Comparison of IQ-TREE and RAxML topologies for the ten data subsets (Fig. 2a-j) using topology tests.

Table S7. Comparison of IQ-TREE topologies derived from “head” and “tail” alignments for the ten data subsets (Fig. 2a-j) using topology tests; tests are repeated using either the “head” or “tail” alignments.

Figure S1. Maximum likelihood tree of 7,541 MIP homologs (IQ-TREE, midpoint rooting). Branch support is indicated as transfer bootstrap expectation values. The ten data subsets that are independently analyzed are indicated in the tree.

Figure S2. Maximum likelihood tree of alignment subset in Fig. 2a (IQ-TREE, midpoint rooting). Branch support is indicated as SH-aLRT and UFBoot, respectively. Taxa are coloured according to taxonomy and MIP clades mentioned in the text are highlighted. Key amino acid residues are shown: NPA boxes, ar/R selectivity filters, Froger residues (P1-5), and conserved residues identified by Abascal et al. (2014) (asterisks).

Figure S3. Maximum likelihood tree of alignment subset in Fig. 2b (IQ-TREE, midpoint rooting). Branch support is indicated as SH-aLRT and UFBoot, respectively. Taxa are coloured according to taxonomy and MIP clades mentioned in the text are highlighted. Key amino acid residues are shown: NPA boxes, ar/R selectivity filters, Froger residues (P1-5), and conserved residues identified by Abascal et al. (2014) (asterisks).

Figure S4. Maximum likelihood tree of alignment subset in Fig. 2c (IQ-TREE, midpoint rooting). Branch support is indicated as SH-aLRT and UFBoot, respectively. Taxa are coloured according to taxonomy and MIP clades mentioned in the text are highlighted. Key amino acid residues are shown: NPA boxes, ar/R selectivity filters, Froger residues (P1-5), and conserved residues identified by Abascal et al. (2014) (asterisks).

Figure S5. Maximum likelihood tree of alignment subset in Fig. 2d (IQ-TREE, midpoint rooting). Branch support is indicated as SH-aLRT and UFBoot, respectively. Taxa are coloured according to taxonomy and MIP clades mentioned in the text are highlighted. Key amino acid residues are shown: NPA boxes, ar/R selectivity filters, Froger residues (P1-5), and conserved residues identified by Abascal et al. (2014) (asterisks).

Figure S6. Maximum likelihood tree of alignment subset in Fig. 2e (IQ-TREE, midpoint rooting). Branch support is indicated as SH-aLRT and UFBoot, respectively. Taxa are coloured according to taxonomy and MIP clades mentioned in the text are highlighted. Key amino acid residues are shown: NPA boxes, ar/R selectivity filters, Froger residues (P1-5), and conserved residues identified by Abascal et al. (2014) (asterisks).

Figure S7. Maximum likelihood tree of alignment subset in Fig. 2f (IQ-TREE, midpoint rooting). Branch support is indicated as SH-aLRT and UFBoot, respectively. Taxa are coloured according to taxonomy and MIP clades mentioned in the text are highlighted. Key amino acid residues are shown: NPA boxes, ar/R selectivity filters, Froger residues (P1-5), and conserved residues identified by Abascal et al. (2014) (asterisks).

Figure S8. Maximum likelihood tree of alignment subset in Fig. 2g (IQ-TREE, midpoint rooting). Branch support is indicated as SH-aLRT and UFBoot, respectively. Taxa are coloured according to taxonomy and MIP clades mentioned in the text are highlighted. Key amino acid residues are shown: NPA boxes, ar/R selectivity filters, Froger residues (P1-5), and conserved residues identified by Abascal et al. (2014) (asterisks).

Figure S9. Maximum likelihood tree of alignment subset in Fig. 2h (IQ-TREE, midpoint rooting). Branch support is indicated as SH-aLRT and UFBoot, respectively. Taxa are coloured according to taxonomy and MIP clades mentioned in the text are highlighted. Key amino acid residues are shown: NPA boxes, ar/R selectivity filters, Froger residues (P1-5), and conserved residues identified by Abascal et al. (2014) (asterisks).

Figure S10. Maximum likelihood tree of alignment subset in Fig. 2i (IQ-TREE, midpoint rooting). Branch support is indicated as SH-aLRT and UFBoot, respectively. Taxa are coloured according to taxonomy and MIP clades mentioned in the text are highlighted. Key amino acid residues are shown: NPA boxes, ar/R selectivity filters, Froger residues (P1-5), and conserved residues identified by Abascal et al. (2014) (asterisks).

Figure S11. Maximum likelihood tree of alignment subset in Fig. 2j (IQ-TREE, midpoint rooting). Branch support is indicated as SH-aLRT and UFBoot, respectively. Taxa are coloured according to taxonomy and MIP clades mentioned in the text are highlighted. Key amino acid residues are shown: NPA boxes, ar/R selectivity filters, Froger residues (P1-5), and conserved residues identified by Abascal et al. (2014) (asterisks).

Figure S12. Maximum likelihood tree of prokaryote MIPs with representative archaeal and bacterial homologs of AqpZ, AqpN, AqpM, AqpX, and GlpF from Finn et al. (2014) and Tesan et al. (2021) (IQ-TREE, midpoint rooting). Branch support is indicated as SH-aLRT and UFBoot, respectively.

Figure S13. Maximum likelihood tree of invertebrate MIPs with representative arthropod MIPs from Stavang et al. (2015) (IQ-TREE, midpoint rooting). Branch support is indicated as SH-aLRT and UFBoot, respectively.

Figure S14. Correlation plot between the number of MIP homologs in the final dataset per eukaryotic supergroup and the number of protein sets (from genomes, transcriptomes and EST collections) in EukProt v. 2 for the different eukaryotic “supergroups”. Pearson’s correlation coefficient and the associated p-value are shown.

Figure S15. Taxonomic distribution of selected MIP clades across eukaryotes with sequenced genomes in our dataset. Bubble size corresponds to the number of MIP paralogs per group annotated in the genomes, and aquaporins (blue) and aquaglyceroporins (yellow) are differentiated (corresponding data in Table S4).

Supplementary Data 1. Alignments for each of the 127 defined MIP paralogy clades showing sequence conservation as both scores and LOGOs (html format).